

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Antibiotic prophylaxis for elective caesarean section: let us cut it down to size

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ABSTRACT

To compare the efficacy of 3 doses of ampicillin prophylaxis regimen with 7 days regimen of ampicillin prophylaxis on infectious morbidity in women undergoing elective caesarean delivery. A prospective non blinded randomized controlled study was conducted on 128 women planned for elective caesarean section. In the study group, patients were given 3 doses: 1 g of IV Ampicillin - 30 minutes preoperatively, later at 6 and 12 hours post operatively. In the control group, patients were given 7 days of antibiotic prophylaxis: IV ampicillin 500 mg - 30 minutes preoperatively, 6 hourly for 24 hours post operatively, followed by oral amoxicillin 500 mg 8 hourly till 7th postoperative days. Patients were followed up till day 7 post operative days for infectious morbidity. No significant difference was found either in the prevalence of postoperative infection or in the mean hospital stays. The cost of the three doses of prophylactic antibiotics was 2/3 rd the cost of the seven days standard postoperative scheme. The usage of minimum doses of prophylactic antibiotics in elective caesarean delivery has an equivalent impact as compared to the conventional seven days regimen in terms of infectious morbidity both on the mother and the neonate with significant reduction in terms of cost of treatment. Shorter regimen is judicious way of use of antibiotics and decreases the workload of the paramedical staff as well.

Keywords: Elective caesarean section; Antibiotic prophylaxis; Antibiotics regimen.

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INTRODUCTION

Caesarean section is the most commonly performed operative procedure in day to day obstetric practice. According to a WHO global survey on maternal and perinatal health (2004-2005) the median rate of caesarean delivery (CD) has been estimated to be 33%, with rates as high as 51% in private hospitals [1]. The data from various resources show that the overall rate of caesarean section in India as a whole is 30% of all deliveries [2].

The rate of caesarean section in our institute has been estimated to be 35% of all deliveries (unpublished data 2014). Out of this, 23% caesarean sections were for elective indications. With increasing CD rates, infections post-CD is posing a significant health and economic burden, making prevention, a public health priority. The practice of caesarean section should be made cost-effective with due emphasis to minimize the infectious morbidity.

Cochrane review (2002) recommends prophylactic ampicillin or first-generation cephalosporins to all high and low risk women undergoing caesarean section [3]. Prophylactic antibiotics have been observed to reduce the incidence of wound infection, endometritis and serious infectious complications by 60-70% as compared to placebo or no treatment [4]. American College of Obstetricians and Gynecologists (ACOG 2010) also recommends the use of single dose of prophylactic antibiotic in all patients undergoing caesarean delivery 1 hour prior to surgery [5].

In developing countries, prolonged use of multiple antibiotics extending to 5-7 days is still prevalent even in elective caesarean deliveries. Factors like malnutrition anemia, blood loss, repeated vaginal examinations, pre labor rupture of membranes, poor social conditions are likely to exacerbate the risk of infectious morbidity associated with caesarean section [6]. The fear of increased morbidity of caesarean section has led the obstetricians to use therapeutic and prolonged doses of multiple antibiotics empirically. The aim of present study was to determine the efficacy and cost benefit of three doses of ampicillin prophylaxis versus the seven day conventional ampicillin /amoxicillin regimen in elective caesarean section in developing country.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This was a prospective non blinded randomized two parallel treatment design study, conducted at Post graduate institute of medical education and research Chandigarh, India in the period from June 2009 and October 2010. The study was approved by the Institutional Ethical Review Board. The sample size were calculated based on the assumption that the true difference between the treatment is 2.00 units and the standard deviation of the response variable is 4.00. A probability value of <0.05 was considered significant and power of the study was fixed to be 80 %. One hundred and twenty eight women planned for elective caesarean section participated in the study. After informed consent and applying exclusion criteria patients were randomly allocated to either study or control group. Randomization was done at the time of admission by computer generated random numbers Those having a co-morbid illness like diabetes/immunosuppressive state/ heart disease, steroids use, anemia, history of blood transfusion, rupture of amniotic membranes >6 hours (hrs), obesity, pyrexia or use of antibiotic in preceding one week were excluded.

Study group: patients received 3 doses: 1 g of IV Ampicillin - 30 minutes preoperatively, repeated at 6 and 12 hours post operatively.

Control group: patients received 500 mg of IV ampicillin - 30 minutes preoperatively, repeated 6 hourly

for first 24 hours post operatively, followed by oral amoxicillin 500 mg 8 hourly till 7th postoperative day (POD).

A detailed history, complete physical examination, routine antenatal investigations and socioeconomic status evaluation was done preoperatively in all patients. The intra operative details like type of anesthesia, disinfectant used for scrubbing incision site, type of skin incision, type of uterine incision, duration of surgery, exteriorization of the uterus done or not, presence or absence of adhesions, associated gut/bladder injury etc were recorded. Complete blood count, urinalysis, and urine culture was done on 2nd post operative day. In case of a suspected wound infection, wound swabs were sent for culture and sensitivity. Blood cultures were sent for those developing pyrexia >38 degrees celsius twice, at least 6 hours apart, after first 24 hours of surgery. Cervical swab was sent if patient complained of purulent lochia. In cases where post operative infection was established, additional and/or alternative antibiotics were prescribed as per culture and sensitivity report.

Most of the patients were discharged on second postoperative day and were followed on the 7th postoperative day. Patients were instructed to report back to the hospital if they suspected any signs of infection. Outcome of the study was assessed on the basis of the following variables: febrile morbidity (>38 degrees Celsius more than once, at least 6 hours apart, after first 24 hours of surgery); endometritis (uterine and abdominal tenderness along with purulent lochia and continued febrile morbidity); urinary tract infection (based on a positive culture report); wound infection (induration, erythema and warmth with purulent discharge). Wound swab culture were taken if discharge was present. The need for additional antibiotics, duration of maternal hospital stay, any other infection anywhere (like mastitis, chest infection), secondary post partum hemorrhage and evidence of neonatal sepsis were also noted.

The unpaired t test and the Chi Square test were used as appropriate for the analysis. Fischer's exact test was also used in place of Chi-square test whenever the number of subjects in any of the cells of the 2 by 2 table was found to be <5 . The data was analyzed through SPSS 16 software.

RESULTS

Figure 1 shows the consort flow chart of this study. A total of 150 patients were assessed for their eligibility to participate in the study and 130 were randomized to participate in the study. Because of the loss of follow up, 128 patients actually participated in the study. The study group and control group constituted 63 and 65 subjects respectively.

Figure 1. Consort flow chart of the study.

Figure 2. Demographic profile of both the groups.

The demographic profile of the two groups with respect to the age, socio economic status, mean gestational age, parity, and BMI was comparable (Figure 2). The indications for caesarean section were similar in the two groups, most common being, breech presentation (38.4% - control group: 28.5% - study group). Most patients underwent surgery through pfannensteil incision (76.2% versus 86.2%). This was statistically insignificant. Both the groups were

comparable with respect to the skill of the operating surgeon, technique of the caesarean, intraoperative adhesions, exteriorization of uterus, duration of surgery and sutures applied (Table 1).

Febrile morbidity occurred in 2 patients in the study group and 3 patients in the control group. Number of patients suffered with urinary tract infection (most common organism - *Escherchia coli*) was 10 (15.8%) and 15 (23%) in the study and control group respectively.

Table 1. Intra operative details of both the groups.

Operative details			
	Study Group (n=63)	Control Group (n=65)	p value
Skin incision			
Pfannenstiel	48 (76.2%)	56 (86.2%)	0.14 (ns)
Vertical	15 (23.8%)	9 (13.8%)	
Adhesions	25 (39.7%)	27 (41.5%)	0.83 (ns)
Gut injury	0	1	0.32 (ns)
Bladder injury	0	0	
Exteriorisation	3	1	0.9 (ns)
Skin sutures			
Silk	50 (79.3%)	50 (76.9%)	0.73 (ns)
Staples	13 (20.7%)	15 (23.1%)	
Mean duration of surgery (min)	60 ± 20.4	58.2 ± 19.2	0.09 (ns)

Table 2. Infectious morbidity of both the groups.

Infectious morbidity					
	Study Group (n=63)	Control Group (n=65)	p value	RR	CI (95%)
Fever	2 (3.2%)	3 (4.6%)	1.00	0.69	0.12- 3.98
Urinary tract infection	10 (15.8%)	15 (23%)	0.31	0.69	0.33-1.41
Wound infection	6 (9.5%)	7 (10.7%)	0.74	0.88	0.31-2.49
Purulent lochia	1 (1.58%)	0	0.49	0	0
Postpartum hemorrhage	1 (1.58%)	0	0.49	0	0
Neonatal sepsis	3 (4.8%)	3 (4.5%)	1.00	1.03	0.22-4.92
Additional antibiotics	17 (26.9%)	24 (36.9%)	0.23	0.73	0.44-1.22

The incidence of wound infection (most common organism - *Staphylococcus aureus*) was 9.5% and 10.7% in the study and control group respectively. Endometritis presenting as purulent lochia with uterine tenderness was present in 1 patient in the study group ($P > 0.05$). The microbiology of cervical swab revealed a group α hemolytic streptococcus sensitive to amikacin. The mean birth weight of the neonate was 2.57 kg and 2.41 kg in the study and control group respectively. There were four admissions each in the neonatal intensive care unit in each group. Three (4.5%) neonates in each group had features of sepsis ($P > 0.05$) and two (3%) neonatal deaths each in the study and control group respectively which was statistically not significant. All the neonates who had sepsis were preterm and weighed less than 1 kg except one newborn in the control group who had septic shock and hypothermia and weighed 2.6 kg. None of the mothers in either group had any predisposing factor for sepsis.

The duration of post operative stay was 4.4 days and 3.8 days in the study group and the control group respectively ($P > 0.05$). Additional antibiotics were given to 26.9% and 36.9% patients in study group and control group ($P > 0.05$) (Table II).

DISCUSSION

Cesarean delivery is often complicated by surgical site infections (SSIs), endometritis and urinary tract infection and antibiotic prophylaxis is known to substantially reduce their incidence. However, the kind of antibiotic and its dosage regimen has always been a matter of debate. Systemic review of Cochrane database (2005) recommended a single dose of prophylactic antibiotic just prior to CS with one or two doses repeated after the CS [7]. There are many studies in the literature comparing single versus multiple doses for antibiotic prophylaxis. Kyihura et al in a randomized, non-blinded comparative study comprising of 288 CS found no statistically significant difference either in the prevalence of postoperative infection or in the mean hospital stays between single combined preoperative dose of gentamicin (160 mg) plus metronidazole (500 mg) versus a post caesarean 7 day conventional regimen of crystalline penicillin (4000000 IU i.v. 6 hourly) and metronidazole (500 mg i.v. 8 hourly) during the first 24 hrs. followed by erythromycin (500 mg) 6 hourly orally along with metronidazole (500 mg) 8 hourly orally till 7th POD. However, the cost-benefit ratio, favored the

single dose regimen as it was effective at approximately one-tenth of the cost of the week long regimen particularly in resource-scarce settings like Mozambique [8].

Antibiotic prophylaxis post-umbilical cord clamping in a similar study comparing single parenteral dose of cefazolin plus metronidazole with its 7 day regimen found a similar protection from infectious morbidity. Although the objective of the study was not to assess the cost effectiveness of either regimen yet the benefit of cost of single dose was quite apparent, the former regime thus being less than one-tenth as expensive as the latter [9].

A randomized clinical trial at Nigeria involving 200 pregnant women undergoing an elective CS found no statistically significant difference in the mean duration of hospital stay, endometritis, urinary tract infection, wound infections, febrile morbidity between the two regimen comparing single dose ceftriaxone (1 g i.v.) with multiple doses of i.v ampiclox (ampicillin and cloxacillin), gentamicin, and metronidazole till 48 hours postoperatively followed by oral ampiclox, oral metronidazole and IM gentamicin at 80 mg 8-hourly, for next 72 hrs followed by oral ampiclox and oral metronidazole till 7th POD. There was a significant statistical difference in the mean cost of antibiotic treatment [10].

Tayyaba Anbreen et al. also compared a triple antibiotic therapy including injection cephradine (500 mg), gentamicin (80 mg) and metronidazole (500 mg) for first 48 hours followed by oral therapy with cephradine and metronidazole for 5 days versus injecton ceftriaxone (500 mg), metronidazole 500 mg intravenously prior to skin incision and repeated 8 hourly for first 48 hours followed by cefixime (400mg) and metronidazole (400 mg) orally for next 5 days. Although both first and third generation cephalosporins were equally effective in preventing complications including febrile illness, dysuria, offensive lochia and abdominal wound infection but there was a significant difference in terms of cost of 3rd generation cephalosporin that was much more than first generation [11].

Another randomized, non-blinding clinical trial of 500 eligible participants (Tanzania) compared surgical-site infection as the primary outcome with 30 days of follow-up. An IV single dose of gentamicin (3 mg/kg) plus metronidazole (500 mg) 30-60 minutes prior to CS was compared with same regimen prior to the operation but continued for 24 hours. Pre-operative single dose antibiotic prophylaxis for emergency caesarean showed a lower cumulative incidence of surgical-site infection, a reduced staff workload and a minimized medication cost compared to multiple doses till 24 hours [12].

Another clinical trial conducted at a tertiary Brazilian centre compared a single intraoperative dose of intravenous 2 g cephalothin, versus a post caesarean

scheme for infection prophylaxis (benzathine penicillin 1,200,000 IU, IM, and procaine penicillin 400,000 IU, IM, every 12 h during the first 48 h), versus no antibiotics of 200 each. Prophylactic use of single dose of cephalothin was associated with decreased postcesarean puerperal infection and presented a cost benefit [13].

The results of the present study are in consistence with the previous studies as the present study also depicts that short term use of prophylactic antibiotic is equally efficacious as compared to their long term use of nearing a week or so in preventing infectious morbidity, surgical site infection, febrile morbidity and limiting hospital stay etc. The cost of three doses regimen was just two third of the seven day regimen with no difference in the cost of the hospital stay. The approximate cost of three doses of ampicillin were 120 INR in comparison 180 INR for the seven day regimen. Shorter regimen is judicious way of use of antibiotics and decreases the workload of the paramedical staff as well.

In the present study the incidence of neonatal sepsis (4.5%) was also same with both the regimens and it was comparable to that of i.v. cefazolin used by Sullivan et al. in 2007 [14].

With reference to the kind of antibiotic to be used for prophylaxis, Systematic review of Cochrane database suggests that both cephalosporins and penicillins represent good choices for prophylaxis in women undergoing CS, although the bacterial resistance, impact on post-discharge maternal and infant infections are not known. More costly extended-spectrum penicillins, second or third generation cephalosporins and combination regimens have not been demonstrated to be more effective [15]. Considering that all the shorter antibiotic regimens have shown similar efficacy in terms of the measured outcomes, the decision of which antibiotic to use shall depend on the prevalence of, regional and hospital based patterns of bacterial isolates and their sensitivity to specific antibiotics, the physician's experience, the cost and availability of antibiotics.

Besides use of antibiotic prophylaxis, the role of strict aseptic techniques and proper hygiene, both pre and post operatively, improving the general nutritional status and other contributing factors cannot be overemphasized. The potential risk of use of multiple doses of broad spectrum antibiotics in causation of drug resistant mutants should also be kept in mind while using antibiotic prophylaxis for long term.

The usage of minimum doses of prophylactic antibiotics in elective caesarean delivery has an equivalent impact as compared to the conventional seven days regimen in terms of infectious morbidity both on the mother and the neonate with significant reduction in the cost of treatment and resources required. Alarming abuse of antibiotic in the form of expensive antibiotics in

multiple doses over several days should be abandoned. Further research may be needed to reveal short- and long-term adverse effects for neonates.

AUTHORS' CONTRIBUTION

SA: Conception and design, Development of methodology, Acquisition of data, Analysis and interpretation of data. MR: Conception and design, Development of methodology, Acquisition of data, Analysis and interpretation of data, Writing, Review and/or revision of the manuscript, Administrative, technical, or material support, Study supervision. SC: Material support, Study supervision. RB: Material support.

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